

A Profile of Deterministic Networking for Cloud-Edge Continuum Computing Platform

Kohei Taniguchi^{†*}, Arata Endo[†], Hirotake Abe[†], Chonho Lee[†], Kundjanasith Thonglek[†], Takahiro Hirofuchi[‡], Ryousei Takano[‡], Takaaki Fukai[‡], Akram Bem Ahmed[‡], Takeharu Kato[‡], Susumu Date[‡]

[†]Osaka University, [‡]National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST)

*taniguchi.kouhei@ais.cmc.osaka-u.ac.jp

I. BACKGROUND

Towards the Post-5G era, we are working on an application platform called Cloud-Edge Continuum Computing Platform (CECC-Platform). CECC-Platform hosts real-time applications over edge and cloud resources on demand, just like serverless computing. To achieve such hosting, a latency-guaranteed network, a network that can deliver packets within the deadline, is useful. A latency-guaranteed network simplifies the estimation of data transfer times and facilitates the design of real-time applications. In addition, when the platform deploys applications on demand, a latency-guaranteed network completes control communications within constant time and reduces deployment time.

Deterministic Networking (DetNet) is a latency-guaranteed network over layer 3 networks. DetNet guarantees packet latency through traffic isolation. There are three types of traffic isolation protocols on switches: priority isolation, bandwidth isolation, and time-slot isolation. Each protocol is suitable for different types of traffic, network scale, and time sync accuracy. To apply DetNet to the platform, we need to select the protocols and set them up appropriately. In other words, we need to create a Detnet profile, which is a document about how to select and configure traffic isolation protocols for CECC-Platform.

In this paper, we aim to create a profile of DetNet for CECC-Platform and investigate missing pieces to apply DetNet for CECC-Platform. This paper is structured as follows. To create the profile, Section 2 summarizes what functionalities are needed in CECC-Platform. In Section 3, we propose a profile for CECC-Platform based on the required functionalities derived in Section 2.

II. REQUIRED FUNCTIONALITIES

To consider the required functionalities when applying DetNet for CECC-Platform, we assume the architecture of the platform as shown in Fig. 1. The platform consists of geographically separated sites connected by DetNet, and all of the sites are managed by Kubernetes (k8s). Each site has computing nodes to deploy k8s pods, message brokers that deliver data from edge devices, and a master clock synced by GPS. DetNet or Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) within each site and DetNet between sites are monitored and reconfigured by an optional network controller or autonomous system.

Fig. 1. Architecture of Cloud-Edge Continuum Computing Platform

Based on this architecture, we derive the required functionalities from the following three questions.

- 1) What kind of traffic needs to be delivered within how long deadline?
- 2) How to coordinate Kubernetes and DetNet?
- 3) Which clock should be used as a reference clock?

For the first question, DetNet needs to deliver two types of traffic - control communications by the platform and data transfer communications by k8s pods and message brokers - within their specific deadlines. Control communications such as heartbeats and requests to the controller are small enough to be delivered with a single packet (less than 1500 Bytes). However, the control communication has a tight timeout value, for example, the default timeout value of Probe, the communication to check whether K8s pods are running, is 1 second. In contrast, the data transfer communications are delivered as one or more packets, and they have different traffic volumes and deadlines. For example, RabbitMQ, a message broker, sends up to 128 MBytes in one data transfer. If this data transfer is performed within 5 seconds, it is equivalent to 86 packets are delivered within 5 seconds. However, delivery of multiple packets within the deadline is tricky for DetNet because DetNet guarantees the latency of one packet. Based on these, the following functionality is required.

- Functionality 1: Delivery of multiple packets within the deadline on DetNet

The second question arises when CECC-Platform deploys applications. At the application deployment, the cluster controller puts k8s pods on the nodes and configures the network between the nodes for data transfer communications within

the deadlines. The key in this process is admission control, which judges whether the network can deliver data transfer communications within the deadlines. If the network cannot deliver the data transfer communication within the deadline, it is necessary to redeploy the application to other nodes. To avoid such redeployment, admission control should be performed before application deployment. In terms of application deployment time, DetNet needs to grasp the available resources and perform admission control quickly. Based on these, the following functionalities are required.

- Functionality 2: Quick admission control of DetNet.
- Functionality 3: Interface for the cluster controller to configure traffic isolation protocols and routing.

Finally, for real-time applications and on-demand deployment of them, it would be ideal if all platform components were perfectly time-synchronized. However, perfect time sync is not possible because of errors when copying a reference clock to each component via networks. This error increases with the distance between the reference clock and the component on the network. For on-demand application deployment, it is important that each node and message broker synchronize its clocks to the nearest reference clock and prevent deployment failures caused by significant time sync errors. In contrast, for DetNet, it is important that switches and sender and receiver nodes on the network route are time-synchronized across them in order to make them work as configured. In DetNet, even small errors in time sync are serious because their effects propagate and accumulate over the network route. Based on these, the following functionalities are required.

- Functionality 4: Selection of reference clocks considering DetNet network paths.
- Functionality 5: Prevention of the cumulative effect caused by time sync errors.

III. PROFILE FOR CECC-PLATFORM

In this section, we propose a profile for CECC-Platform based on the functionality derived in Section 2.

A. Traffic specification (Functionality 1, 2, 3)

More traffic specifications in addition to traffic amount and deadline become available, it will be easier and faster to perform admission control to guarantee the latency of multiple packets. Such a variety of traffic specifications are available through RFC 9016, which specifies the characteristics and requirements of traffic in DetNet [1].

To obtain the traffic specification following RFC 9016 at the application deployment, it shall be predefined by an application developer. For example, Knative, a framework to deploy event-driven applications on Kubernetes, supports the definition of communication as an event, so it is recommended that such a framework is used for the pre-definition of traffic specifications.

B. Guaranteed latency of multiple packets (Functionality 1)

“Shaper Parameter Settings for Bursty Traffic Requiring Bounded Latency” (P802.1Qdq) supports guaranteed latency

of multiple packets [2]. As the name states, P802.1Qdq provides how to configure traffic isolation protocols to guarantee the latency of multiple packets even produced burstily. Based on P802.1Qdq, DetNet for the platform should use different protocols for two types of traffic. For the traffic that sends one packet at a high frequency, such as control communication, it is better to use a Time-Aware Shaper, which isolates traffic using time slots, because it ensures that traffic is forwarded within the configured time period. In contrast, for the bursty traffic that sends multiple packets in a short term, such as data transfer, it is better to use Credit-Based Shaper and Strict Priority Filter, which isolate traffic by bandwidth and priority isolation because it can send a sequence of packets efficiently.

C. Network domain partitioning (Functionality 2, 4, 5)

DetNet and TSN should be partitioned by network domains, an area of the network that can perform admission control and guarantee latency independently. A smaller network domain makes the time sync and the admission control in each domain easy because the number of switches and the average length of network routes become smaller. Specifically, the distance between the switch and the reference clock of each domain becomes smaller, resulting in more accurate time sync. Also, admission control in each domain spends less time because it checks fewer switches on the network route.

A side effect of partitioning network domains is the connectivity between domains must be considered. Basically, each network domain guarantees the latency following such as RFC 9023 about connectivity between IP network-based DetNet and TSN [3]. However, a traffic specification may change through a network domain because the arrival interval of packets and other factors may be changed. In this case, the later network domains may fail to guarantee the latency. Recovering the original traffic specification at the border of the network domains can prevent such failure [4].

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Varga, J. Farkas, R. Cummings, Y. Jiang, *et al.*, *Flow and Service Information Model for Deterministic Networking (DetNet)*, RFC 9016, Mar. 2021.
- [2] *P802.1Qdq – Shaper Parameter Settings for Bursty Traffic Requiring Bounded Latency*, <https://1.ieee802.org/tsn/802-1qdq/>, (Accessed on 01/11/2024).
- [3] B. Varga, J. Farkas, A. G. Malis, and S. Bryant, *Deterministic Networking (DetNet) Data Plane: IP over IEEE 802.1 Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN)*, RFC 9023, Jun. 2021.
- [4] J. Joung and J. Kwon, *Zero Jitter for Deterministic Networks without Time-Synchronization*, IEEE Access, 2021.